

The Influence of Economic Factor on Domestic Violence Against Men in Iringa Municipality

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Abstract:- This study examined the Influence of economic factors on domestic violence against men within the Iringa Municipality. The research employed qualitative methodologies with a sample of 30 adult married men from six different cases within Iringa. The data analysis was carried out using thematic analysis. Findings revealed that economic situations such as income poverty, unemployment and involvements in productivity were causes for violence. The study concluded economic factors influenced domestic violence against men. The study recommends that the government should take proactive measures to address all economic factors which results into domestic violence against men.

Keywords:- Domestic Violence, Domestic Violence Against Men, Economic Factors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Domestic violence is a form of mistreatment that takes place within a household, such as in marriages, cohabitation, or between intimate partners. Domestic violence against men involves acts of punishment, sexual abuse, bullying, and various other forms of violence directed towards men. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), domestic violence against men is a significant threat to men's well-being worldwide. (Notably, a substantial portion of the affected men has previously engaged in violent behavior towards their partners) Additionally, statistics indicate that about 10.6% to 40% of men have experienced abuse or maltreatment during their childhood. Factors like alcohol abuse, jealousy, mental health issues, physical disabilities and shorter relationship durations are all linked to a higher exposure to experiencing domestic violence against men (WHO, 2016). United Kingdom survey (Lövestad *et al.*, 2012) found that 9 percent of men's, roughly translating to 1.4 million men, had encountered partner abuse encompassing stalking, physical violence, and sexual assault. These findings highlight the prevalence of domestic violence against men, although most data stem from developed nations.

Aye *et al.*, (2018) conducted a study in Nigeria, focusing on domestic violence among working couples. The study identified various forms of domestic violence experienced by both men and women, such as hitting, slapping, intimidation, marital rape and fighting. Dlamini (2021) noted that COVID-19 increased violence against men in Africa. This highlights the current harshness of domestic

violence against men and its hindrance to their potential. These issues are linked with common causes and consequences rooted in social, economic and cultural factors. Poverty, gender inequality, social norms, and limited access to education, including sexual education, contribute to DVaM (Burton, 2016). In the context of Tanzania, Nkonjera (2020) highlighted lack of legal protection for men facing domestic violence. Existing laws addressing violence against men are insufficiently prepared to address the unique circumstances and gender dynamics of violence against men. Consequently, there is an extensive domestic violence problem targeting men in Tanzania.

Moreover, URT, (2022) noted that Article 21 of the same Protocol calls for the States to ensure that laws on GBV provide for the comprehensive testing, treatment and care of survivors of sexual offences, which include; emergency contraception, ready access to post exposure prophylaxis at all health facilities to reduce the risk of contracting HIV, and preventing the onset of sexually transmitted infections. On the other hand, Article 11 of the said Addendum to the 1997 Declaration calls for, inter alia, establishment of the special counseling services, legal and police units to provide dedicated and sensitive services to survivors of violence. Kalage (2020) stressed the need for research into domestic violence against men, as most studies address violence against women. This study thus aims to explore the influence economic factors on domestic violence against men in Iringa Municipality.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ Theoretical Literature Review

- *Power Control Theory*

John Hagan (1987) proposed a theory to explain the differences in crime rates between men and women. The power control theory, derived from control theories, suggests that individuals would engage in deviant behavior if not controlled by social control. According to this theory, family plays a crucial role in employing control during early life. Lack of control within the family leads to increased freedom and behavior choices. Hagan (1987) further distinguished these ideas, demonstrating that the transition to more egalitarian family structures had the greatest impact on mother-father relationships, resulting in an increase in domestic violence against men (DVaM). This study recognizes the importance of economic, cultural, and social factors in contributing to Domestic Violence against Men, as women gain more power in these areas. The power control

theory integrates feminist theories, Marxist theories, and control theories to explain the variations in crime rates among men and women. Therefore, this study examines the influence of economic on Domestic Violence against Men. It acknowledges the attention given to violence against men, which arises from economic circumstances. The power control theory found in economic factors can provide harmony among the family's members.

- *Empirical Literature Review*

Cao *et al.*, (2014) examined the role of income disparities in assessing support and resources for men victims. The study emphasizes the challenge faced by economically disadvantaged men in seeking help and legal aid. Likewise, the current study is related with Aye *et al.*, (2018) carried out in Zone B District of Benue state, Nigeria to examine social factors associated with domestic violence among working couples. A sample size of 235 married men and women selected using stratified simple random sampling technique. Regression analysis and were used in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study identified types of domestic violence among working couples to include hitting, slapping, beating, intimidation, marital rape and fighting amongst others which were mostly caused by economic factors including poverty.

In addition, Dutton and White (2013) focused that domestic violence is one of the major problems and men also suffer from domestic violence at the hands of their wives or intimate partners whereby unemployment's was among the cause of it. Efforts to prevent domestic violence and its successful implementation have followed years of research and advocacy on behalf of their victims. New laws, police procedures, medical and forensic research have improved the conditions of men who suffer from domestic violence. In recent years, domestic violence has become a hot topic among activists, individuals, and many organizations. After decades of research, many political activists are now shouting this at the top of their voice that both men and women can be victims of domestic violence in roughly the equal number. Despite several studies that have suggested that only women can face domestic violence at the hands of men, the other empirical studies suggest that the victims of domestic violence can be both men and women. This has provoked the enthusiastic men gender activists that policymakers should keep in mind regarding the policies related to domestic violence who made policies and laws mainly focusing on women. In addition, it was explained that economic factors such as poverty and unemployment's caused domestic violence against men.

Also, Mahoney (2013) who said that some abusers impose physical injury to parts of the body which is not normally seen in the legs and privates' part of the body due to men being not involved in productivity. That means that men are physically harmed and affected by physical violence especially men who drink too much because of not being practiced in production. Drinking too much makes men losing control during physical fight. Djamba and Kimuna, (2015) found that many physical symptoms reported by abused women were similar with being injury, kicked, pushed and being harmed by strong objects because

men are not producing. From this study results and discussion therefore, the study concludes among the physical effect violence on men in Iringa Municipal was social factors such as religious, education and political practices. Thus, almost all cases justified the influence economic factors on domestic violence against men. All these arguments from all six cases justify that economic factor influencing domestic violence against men in Iringa municipality. Street and Dardis (2018) explained that gender is socially constructed and is influenced by many factors. It is a device that is used by society to control its members. Gender sometimes as social class and race can be used to make stereotypes and prejudices against people. Prejudices are a set of attitudes that are offensive to one section of the society, while discrimination is the overt negativity towards a person depending on his superfluous identity.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Iringa Municipality, located in the southern highland zone of Tanzania. The study focused on adult married men who were heads of households were affected by domestic violence. The study involved six wards of Kihesa, Kitanzini, Kwakilosa, Mivinjeni, Mkwawa and Nduli in Iringa Municipality. The study was conducted qualitatively. A case study design was selected since it allowed an in-depth examination of one or a few cases, in contrast to a more superficial cross-sectional study of a large sample (Kothari, 2014).

The design was selected since the purpose was to illuminate the specific information through qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions and respondents experience (Hyett and Dickson 2014). The case study allows collecting data at specified time within specified location. In this study the sample size was 30 adult married men who reported to have domestic violence from the six wards representing other men in the study area. Selection of respondents was a snowball where in the first stage the researcher contacted the Community Development Officers at Iringa Municipality who had information related to violence against men. The Community Development Officers assisted to get respondents from the six wards who were believed to have attributes related purpose of the study. The data were analyzed qualitatively using content analysis through organizing, recording, categorization and grouping into major recurring themes based on specific objectives (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). Thereafter, the results were presented using explanations and direct quotations from the respondents. In due course of this research, the researcher adhered to the following ethical standards such as designing anonymous research guide, safeguarding confidentiality and making sure that no part of the collected data used without acceptance of university. In addition, the researcher requested clearance letter from the university through that also requested permission from Municipal director office. Doing so ensured research ethics.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Economic Factors That Influencing Domestic Violence Against Men*

Economic factors encompassed issues such as income poverty, unemployment, and involvement in productive activities. These thematic areas were believed to be important in this study because it was assumed that they could contribute to domestic violence against men in Iringa Municipal, yet there was limited empirical evidence to support the existence and impact of these themes. The following findings emerged from the interviews.

➤ *Influence of Income Poverty on Domestic Violence Against Men*

Income poverty was believed important to lead to DVaM. It was found that it contributed to domestic violence against men in assumption that, when men experienced economic hardship and were economically disadvantaged, it can lead to frustration, powerless and stress. These emotions can exacerbate conflict within a relationship and potentially escalated into domestic violence to men. Therefore, income poverty can serve as a factor that influences domestic violence against men. There was response related to this factor as quoted below.

“I have experienced that families that are suffering from income poverty due to unstable economic situation men were suffering with violence from their wives because family need food, and other important need. Such kind of violence was important to push men to fight more for obtaining family needs (Kihesa/ Key respondents/ 35 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Lack of handling family matters because of poverty women become aggressive to their husbands and violate men because they were economically weak due to income poverty. Through interviews it was confirmed that:

“Due to the small income, I struggle to manage the cost of living, leading my wife to exploit me. My job as a truck driver for cargo isn't sufficient for my family. The boss condition oppresses me; whenever the truck breaks down, the repair costs are deducted from my salary. This leaves me with very little that doesn't meet my family's needs. Consequently, I face mistreatment through insults, disrespect, and even denial of married rights by my wife (Kwakilosa/ Key respondents/ 55 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Through interviews it was noted out that some women used their time more for economic situation. This led to poor relationship, and once argued by men conflicts raised because most of women were overconfidence when they have higher income compared to their husbands. The respondents confirmed that:

“Women nowadays have reduced respecting to their husband in which led fighting at family level. Men feel that they are not being respected because of poverty, women are the one that provides basic needs to the family that why they

violate men (Mivinjeni/ Key respondents/38 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Men need respect from their wives but wives did not respect them because of poverty, the key respondents insisted that:

“Women nowadays have reduced respecting their husband due to poverty which led fighting at family level. Men feel that not being respected is violence to them because of believers and traditional practices. According to our culture (Hehe) we are required to be respected by our wives, but currently things are changes. Women are as busy as, we lack the traditional respect, due to that traditionally we are violated” (Nduli/ Key respondents/52years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Through interview with key respondents, it was confirmed that economic situation in the form of income poverty led to violence against men. That means if men were not able to support family needs they were not given sexual need from wives. During interviews it was explained that:

“I'm staying in this area and I have experienced that we men we like to be trusted and dominate our family in term of income and ruling. If we always get support from our wives that to us is shame and is a kind of violence against us” (Mkwawa/ Key respondents/ 31years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Other respondents agreed that lack of income to men caused psychological violence to men since most of the time men were given important need from their wives. Such kind of situation psychologically affected their presence as men at the family level. These results were justified by respondents who noted out that:

“Violence against men happens to some of the families because, some men are facing income poverty, so women are the one fighting for the family they ensure all basic need of the family are stable so they feel even tired so they start to abuse their husband that they are lazy to find money. As a result, psychologically men feel that they violated” (Kwakilosa/ Key respondents/ 48years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

In addition, key respondents witnessed that income poverty caused violence to their husband since women expected resolving human need at family level from their husbands but as a result it was difficult because they were not able to contribute to family needs. As confirmed by key respondents that:

“In this area income poverty affects family stability and good relationship because without money it is difficult to generate family needs. Due to that, women become very bitter which to men is a violence” (Kitanzini/ Key respondents/ 50years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Therefore, the study realized that in poverty factors influenced domestic violence against men. The violence was based much on physical harassment, sexual and psychological violence. Lack of money for handling family situation was the main cause of domestic violence against men. Some men their income was not satisfying family needs which became source of violence.

The findings are similar with Cao *et al.*, (2014) focused that the role of income disparities in assessing to support and resources for men victims. The study emphasizes the challenge faced by economically disadvantaged men in seeking help and legal aid. Likewise, the current study is related with Aye *et al.*, (2018) the study identified types of domestic violence among working couples to include hitting, slapping, beating, intimidation, marital rape and fighting amongst others which were mostly caused by economic factors including poverty.

A study conducted by Zegenhagen *et al.*, (2019) found that men who lived in household with lower level of income were more likely to experience domestic violence than men who lived in house hold with higher level of income. Specifically, the study found that men who lived in household with incomes below the poverty line were more likely to experience physical violence, emotional abuse, and sexual violence from their partners than men who lived in house hold with incomes above the poverty line. Economic stress and financial strain contribute to the perpetration of domestic violence against men, in that men who experienced economic stress and financial strain were more likely to engage in abusive behavior towards their partners as the way of exerting control and coping with stress. Also, the study conducted by Yakubovich *et al.*, (2018) support the findings of the current study in that male victimization within intimate relationship, is a result of men in lower income were at higher risk of experiencing domestic violence. This finding underscores the potential economic stressors that can exacerbate tension within relationship and leading to abusive behavior.

➤ *Influence of Unemployment on Domestic Violence Against Men*

Through interview with key respondents, it was revealed that unemployment led to violence against men. That means when men lose their job or they don't have a stable job some men experience feelings of frustration, inadequacy or emasculation due to their unemployment which could lead to the tension and conflict at home. During interviews it was explained that:

"I don't have a stable job that brings in a substantial income. I am temporary labor, called "Deiwaka," and I earn between three thousand to six thousand shillings per day. As we're considering other ways to improve our financial situation, my wife has started mistreating me, even attack me. Whenever I try to talk to her, she doesn't listen and it's like she's ignoring me" (Kwakilosa/ Key respondents/ 36years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

• *As Confirmed by key Respondents that:*

"Because of our financial struggles, my wife mistreats and mock me, using hurtful names like "mwaume suruali," because I couldn't buy her the things she wanted as a woman. Her needs were expensive, and I couldn't manage them. This had a psychological impact on me, especially when she would say these things in front of my friends and even to our children so she decided to leave home and go to his uncle and leave the children with me but I didn't give her divorce" (Kitanzini/ Key respondents/ 44 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Unemployment result into domestic violence against men because men do not provide the important requirements to their wives which led to mis understanding. Also, unemployment result to stress and frustration within their households. In certain cases, these difficult circumstances might lead to women resorting to aggressive behavior as a way to cope or assert control in their lives. The combination of financial strain and emotional distress can unfortunately result in instances of domestic violence, where women might engage in harmful actions towards their partners or family.

The findings are similar with Dutton and White (2013) focused that domestic violence is one of the major problems and men also suffer from domestic violence at the hands of their wives or intimate partners whereby unemployment was among the cause of it.

Similar to Dom *et al.*, (2016) findings, men who experience long term, unemployment were more likely to experience domestic violence than men who were employed or who experienced only short-term unemployment. Specifically, the study found that men who were unemployed for more than one year were more likely to experience physical violence, emotional abuse, and sexually violence from their partners than men who were employed. In addition, economic stress and financial strain contribute to the perpetration of domestic violence against men, leading to men with economic stress and financially strain to engage in abusive behavior towards their partners as a way of exerting control and coping with stress. Also, Schneider *et al.*, (2016) add to the present study that the period of unemployment was associated with a higher risk of experiencing domestic violence., this suggests that economic stressors often accompanying unemployment, can exacerbate tension within relationship, potentially.

➤ *Influence of Involvement in Productivity on Domestic Violence Against Men.*

The absence of productive engagement might result in a sense of powerlessness, and individual may struggle to cope with these feelings in healthy ways. This emotional confusion can manifest in arguments, conflicts and even violence as an outlet for the accumulated stress.

"Many men have been experiencing violence from their wives. As you can see because they tend to spend long hours in alcohol clubs from morning till midnight, neglecting productive activities that would support both themselves and their families. This behavior leads to conflict

within their families. Consequently, many of these men have been physically abused by their wives, resulting in severe injuries and scars on their bodies” (Kwakilosa/ Key respondents/ 45 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

“Men sometimes are not much working hard to produce farm products as a result they are engaged much on drinking local beers which makes women to be aggressive and fighting against each other. Doing so affects men psychologically which is a violence against them” (Kitanzini/ Key respondents/ 49 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

- *Other Respondents Noted That;*

“Violence against men happens to some of the families because, some men are facing income poverty and this is because they are not producing much, they lack money, they are not fit economically. All these situation makes men being dominated and violated (Mivinjeni/ Key respondents/ 56 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

During interviews it was explained that: “Men who produce various products and generate income are the one who live peacefully and there is very minimal violence against men (Kihesa/ Key respondents/ 52 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

The arguments above were supported by other respondents who argued that: “Productivity with effects to high income generation are weapons for stopping up violence from women. We work hard because we avoid violence from women” (Nduli/ Key respondents/ 30 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

In some families it was recognized that men were not involved in productivity, they were much involved in drinking alcohol. Drinking much was the source of violence against men. During interviews it was found that: “Women were not happy with men who were drinking all the time. This kind of behavior because a source of fighting at household level (Kwakilosa/ Key respondents/33 years old/ Men/ Iringa Municipality 11, August 2023).

Findings in this study is related with arguments made by Mahoney (2013) in that some abusers they impose the physical injury to parts of the body which is not normally seen in the legs and privates’ part of the body due to men being not involved in productivity. That means that men are physically harmed and affected by physical violence especially men who drink too much because of not being practiced in production. Drinking too much makes men lose control during physical fight. The study is also related with Djamba and Kimuna, (2015) who found that many physical symptoms reported by abused partners were similar with being injury, kicked, pushed and being harmed by strong objects. Thus, almost all cases justified the influence economic factors on domestic violence against men. All these arguments from all six cases justify that economic factor influenced domestic violence against men in Iringa municipality. In addition, the findings are similar with

Węziak-Białowolska et al., (2020) that indicated that men who felt disconnected from productive activities were at higher risk of experiencing domestic violence. This highlights the potential psychological stressors that can result from a perceived lack of purpose or involvement, potentially contributing to abusive behaviors.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ *Conclusion*

It is concluded that, economic factors such as income poverty, unemployment and lack of men being involved in production activities was the cause of violence against men. Men who experience economic hardship lead an increased tension and conflict within the family which may escalate into violence against men. Also, the results show that economic factor has a higher impact on domestic violence against men in Iringa municipality compared to other factors.

➤ *Recommendation*

It is in the light of the study findings; the researcher recommends the following action to be taken into considerations: the governments should implement policies and program that aim to reduce poverty, unemployment and less involvement in productivity. Also, the government can promote financial inclusion and provide access to credit and other financial services to support economic empowerment to men. The legal force unit (gender desk) dealing with domestic violence should provide education and awareness related with domestic violence

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